

EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONAL MANAGEMENT: PEDAGOGICAL AND DISTRIBUTED LEADERSHIP-A COMPETENCIES BASED LEARNING MODEL

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Abstract

This paper is structured in two main sections: the first describes competency-based learning, and the second analyzes strategic educational management as an alternative to traditional management, with an emphasis on leadership competency. This paper aims to establish a link between this educational model and the management of educational institutions; that is to say, the competence-based approach is presented as a teaching-learning model whilst contributing to educational management. The purpose then, without wishing to exhaust the question, was to contribute to the debate about the improvement of educational quality through innovation and to analyze what is the role that the management of centers plays in this process that we believe consists of transforming schemes and old models in education and management. In this line, the competencies approach was shown to be transversal, because we could see what a contribution means as a teaching model as well as a management model. This is the product of conceiving organizations as units of meaning, and not as isolated compartments of students, teachers, managers, and families. The feedback that we observe between management and learning through the competency model is due to this obligation to build learning communities around educational systems. Conclusion of the study indicate that competency-based learning mechanism and the strategies of analyzing the educational management in precise on leadership competencies. Moreover, previous literature also demonstrated the key concept that are related to the educational prospective and learning mechanism to the competency enhancement and skill development.

Keywords: competence-based learning, strategic educational management, pedagogical and distributed leadership.

INTRODUCTION

Education currently faces many changes and challenges (Potra et al., 2021). This section aims to summarize, by way of introduction, some of those challenges that are the product of paradigm shifts at the internal level, but that are based on transformations that have occurred at the social level (Vesan & Pansardi, 2021). These new demands come in part from the current information and knowledge society (Konno & Schillaci, 2021). Knowledge is accumulating faster and faster in all areas (Liu & Corma, 2021), while it is spread very quickly through new

means of communication (Bara et al., 2021), and is translated into technological applications that modify our lives (Chen & Segev, 2021).

This phenomenon has several consequences for the educational system. Among them (Potra et al., 2021), there is an increasing tendency to think of curricula in terms of skills and abilities that students must develop (Potra et al., 2021), one of which is precisely the ability to search for and process information (Xazratov et al., 2021).

Faced with constant change as a hallmark of our era, it is the set of elements that make up the educational system that is obsolete (Рахмонова, 2021). Broadly speaking, we can say that compared to the classic didactic positions centered on the classroom and on the teacher's activity (Beltrán Lainez, 2021), today's teaching centered on the autonomous activity of the student is advocated (Cheng & Ding, 2021), with curricular proposals more adapted to the requirements of productive life and community (Vilanova et al., 2021).

Two great challenges are common to all human organizations today (Shaikh et al., 2021). On the one hand, redefine its mission, build a new vision that guides its work and, simultaneously (UNESCO, 2022. p 131), look for new forms of organization (Karimova, 2022), break the old structures for more flexible ones that allow it to adapt to changing environments (Hustad & Olsen, 2022).

Educational systems do not escape this general situation (Weiss & Mattern, 2021). In this context, it is necessary to rethink where schools should go and how they should be organized and conducted (Fiş Erümit et al., 2021); that is, to review both the objectives they seek to achieve in society, as well as their ways of organizing and functioning to capture them (Miceli et al., 2021). We must respond to this cultural change from education but bearing in mind that organization and management must also be part of this transformation (Dimitrovski et al., 2021), both at the level of the government of education and at educational centers (Shaturaev, 2021).

Somehow, we are halfway through this challenge (Yin et al., 2022), because we have built new visions, but it is very difficult for us to break the old structures (Syvertsen et al., 2021). Today no one doubts, for example, that education should be centered on the student rather than the teacher (Zhao & Watterston, 2021), however, educational practices do not accompany this conviction (O'Brien et al., 2021); In general, we continue to repeat traditional methods and forms of organization (Aliyarovich & Sayfiddinovich, 2021).

In this scenario of change, the management of centers faces several challenges that imply certain transformations (García-Peñalvo, 2021). One of them could be called "Curriculum and transformation" (Mensah et al., 2020); that is to say, the new teaching-learning models have curricular innovation among their objectives (Regis-Hernández et al., 2022) and it is necessary for educational management to consciously assume these new demands (Meyer & Norman, 2020).

So that this study is crossed by certainty: making an option for an educational model requires specific management and a high level of professional competence on the part of managers (Lee

et al., 2020). This is the foundation and relevance of this work that aims, through bibliographic research (Marchiori & Franco, 2020), to present a learning model that is attentive to these challenges and to examine what type of educational management is required (Harper & Neubauer, 2021). Ultimately, the question is: what type of management has a positive impact on learning? (Mason & Grijalva, 2019).

This research is divided into two main sections: first, the competency-based learning model is characterized, and then strategic educational management is analyzed as an alternative to traditional management, with an emphasis on leadership skills (Yang et al., 2021). They will try to establish lines of synergy between this educational model and the management of centers (Sherlock & Wagstaff, 2019); that is, the competencies approach is presented as a teaching-learning model (Paliwal & Singh, 2021), and as a contribution that illuminates educational management. Some questions that guide this research are:

- What are the objectives and importance of a competency-based learning model?
- What is the role of educational management/direction in this model? How should this management/direction be for the success of the competency-based learning model?
- What are the essential competencies of the manager for the implementation of this approach?
- What practices favor the construction of leadership? How does this influence the improvement of educational quality?

The Learning Model Based On Competencies

The expression competencies are widely extended in the world of education (Brundiens et al., 2021), although this concept is understood in different ways and different meanings are assigned to it, not always coinciding. There is, however, broad consensus that has made it possible to develop training programs based on convergence between countries, such as the Tuning Project (Eizaguirre et al., 2019).

The following table summarizes the pedagogical principles underlying the competency-based approach:

Table 1: Pedagogical principles of the competency-based model

Sr#	Competencies
1.	The aim of the school is not to transmit information but to provoke development of basic skills.
2.	The goal of teaching will be for students to reconstruct their models' vulgar minds, their thought schemes
3.	The development of competencies requires focusing on real situations and offers authentic activities. Find anchors with everyday life.
4.	Provide warm, safe, and free environment.
5.	Evaluation must be understood as formative.
6.	The role of the teacher is to tutor learning.
7.	The spatial and temporal organization of school contexts must consider the flexibility and creativity required by the nature of authentic tasks and by the demands of bonding with the social environment.
8.	Promote cooperation between equals. It includes dialogue, debate and discrepancy, respect for differences, knowing how to listen, enriching oneself with others and having generosity to offer the best of oneself.
9.	Stimulate each student's metacognition, their ability to understand and govern their own learning process.
10.	Preparation of learning environments characterized by the exchange and experience of the most alive and elaborated culture.
11.	Learn in situations of uncertainty and in permanent processes of change, it is a condition for learning to learn.
12.	Provoking relevant learning requires actively involving the student in processes of search, study, experimentation, reflection, application, and communication of the knowledge.

It is interesting to point out two issues that arise from these principles and that we understand are central to education today. First, the school can encourage students to distort their thought patterns, their beliefs, and basic representations, to behave autonomously and be protagonists in the construction of knowledge (Rubegni et al., 2022). To denature means to question, to problematize reality. Second, that education should promote the ability to dialogue in discrepancies, which is precisely democracy in the broad sense (Anderson et al., 2019).

The various definitions of the concept of competence respond to different sources, perspectives, and epistemologies. In some cases (Sengul et al., 2020), these positions indicate more operative components than conceptual ones (Arrieta et al., 2020).

Among these operational definitions is the one proposed by the United States Department of Education in 2001 as a framework for the development of a national system of standards, evaluation, and certification of abilities and skills. There it is pointed out that competence is a combination of skills, abilities, and knowledge necessary to perform a specific task (Voorhees, 2001; Rahardja et al., 2018).

The following table includes other definitions of competence that complete and enriches the question:

Sr#	Authors	Definitions
1.	Wheatley (1999)	Complex know-how, the result of integration, mobilization, and adaptation capabilities (knowledge, attitudes, and skills) used effectively in situations that have a common character.
2.	Kouzes and Posner (1995)	Dynamic combination of knowledge, understanding, skills and abilities.
3.	Bennis and Nanus (1985)	Ability to effectively deal with a family of analogous situations, mobilizing conscientiously and quickly, relevant, and creative, multiple resources cognitive: knowledge, skills, micro skills, information, values, attitudes, perception schemes, evaluation, and reasoning.
4.	Gardner (1990)	The three great dimensions that make up any competence are: to know (knowledge), know-how (skills) and be (attitudes).
5.	(Chaleff, 1995, p. 3)	The ability of students to apply knowledge and skills, and to analyze, reason and communicate effectively when pose, solve, and interpret problems related to different situations.
6.	(Zaleznik, 1977)	Combination of practical skills, knowledge, motivation, ethical values, attitudes, emotions, and other components social and behavioral mobilize together to achieve an effective action.
7.	(Diekelmann et al., 2007)	Set of knowledge, skills and attitudes that must be integrated to do a specific task.
8.	McClelland and Burnham (1976)	Comprehensive actions to identify, interpret, argue, and solve problems with suitability and ethical commitment, mobilizing the different knowledges: to be, to do and meet.

Indeed, reviewing the literature on this subject, one of the first aspects that stands out is the multiplicity of definitions that exist of competence. When reviewing the content of these, it is important to synthesize and comment on some particularities:

- a) Although knowledge is a key element of competence, it is not enough to be competent. In more explanatory definitions, capacities, skills, motivations, and attitudes also appear. We see that the competencies have a holistic and integrated character (Chen et al., 2021).
- b) Training people and professionals through competency-based orientation also implies that this knowledge is put into effective practice in the real world. So, when considering the teaching of skills, what we are trying to do is facilitate the ability to transfer learning, which has generally been presented out of context, to situations close to reality. Here we appreciate the contextual nature of the skills and the creative nature of the transfer (Xie et al., 2021).
- c) Competence is not something directly observable but is inferred from the interpretation of performances; it is related to a capacity in action to respond to changing situations. Competencies involve a permanent process of reflection to harmonize intentions with the possibilities of each context (Konttila et al., 2019).
- d) Competence supposes knowledge (conceptual), know-how (procedural), and know-how (attitudinal), in accordance with what is also indicated in the report of MARY O'KEEFE (2007, p. 70). We can observe here the ethical dimension of competencies, which are nourished by attitudes, values, and commitments that people adopt (Salman et al., 2020).
- e) They have an evolutionary character. They develop, refine, expand, or deteriorate and constrain throughout life (DiFrisco et al., 2022).

The purpose of education, and of competency-based education, is the full development of the human being. This means showing, as the authors do, that competence transcends the professional field and affects the person's life. Assuming this premise, it is possible to propose specific and generic competencies, thus contemplating the social, interpersonal, personal, and professional spheres; an accent on the alluded-to integrality of education today (Levine & Patrick, 2019).

Thus, considering the possible classifications of competencies, one is presented that tries to be comprehensive, following the Guide for the evaluation of competencies in social sciences (Lewallen & McMullan, 2001, p. 75), which divides them into:

- Specific skills, which are specific to a field or degree and are aimed at achieving a specific profile of the graduate. These are particular and precise to an area or content of its own and result in the resolution of complex tasks (Motsch et al., 2021).
- Generic skills, which are common to most degrees. Within this block we find personal skills such as time management and responsibility for learning itself; interpersonal skills, such as communicating, working in a team, leading, or negotiating. These competencies are transversal to the entire training process, uniformly integrating the curriculum of a career in relation to the main lines that mark the profile of an institution (Nor et al., 2019).

Changes and Modifications in Model

In a way, we could understand that the term competence was born as a response to the limitations of traditional teaching (Christie, 2018). More precisely, "the difficulty in teaching competencies is given (Ostermann et al., 2018) because the way of teaching them involves activities far removed from the school tradition" (Jonson et al., 2020; Shaturaev, 2021). According to the authors, our tradition, based on the verbal transmission and literal reproduction of what has been learned, does not encourage the implementation of a competency-based learning model. This demands significance and e in learning, requires having to start from the previous knowledge of the students, consider personal motivations, offer challenges, and help according to the real possibilities of each one (Jaswal & Akhtar, 2019).

Likewise, it should be underlined that competencies have a procedural and functional nature, learning by doing, and teaching for complexity. However, the inherited school is based on the knowledge and power of the teacher, and not on the know-how of the student; the ability to reproduce is valued more than the ability to apply (Sutaphan & Yuenyong, 2019).

It is necessary to redefine the role of the student and the teacher within the framework of this educational approach. The students appear as managers of their own learning and not as mere depositaries of it (Adams et al., 2020). The purpose is that they:

- Be able to search, select and process the information received to create knowledge and apply it autonomously.

- Learn to face the uncertainties inherent to knowledge and assume that the solution of some problems generates others.
- Learn to live together, actively participating in a globalized, interrelated and changing world.
- Acquire ethical training, which is obtained, beyond the contents of a subject, through a constant exercise of reflection and democratic practice. (Basic Competences Group of the Ministry of Education of Cantabria, 2007, pp. 13 and 14)

For his part, the teacher becomes a facilitator of this process that seeks the autonomy of the student. He must promote the construction of knowledge, critical reflection and the use or application of acquired knowledge, always in significant contexts so that learning acquires meaning. This new profile must influence the role of the teacher, who from mere transmission must move on to provoking the reconstruction of knowledge from the student's experience (Verduijn & Berglund, 2019).

It is essential to question whether the teacher stands as a simple possessor and transmitter of knowledge; or if he, on the contrary, assumes the role of mediator and guide in the construction of knowledge and in the full development of the individuality of his students. Both ways of understanding this task imply different consequences and presuppose a prior conception of truth (Hong & Lin, 2019). In the first case, this is understood as a pre-existing reality and the student as a deposit of that truth to be transmitted; while in the second case, the truth is conceived as a common construction and process towards an inexhaustible knowledge, the result of historical contingency and evolution, but always according to vital human experience (Lynch, 2018).

In this second line, the model of competencies is placed, as we have seen. It is not the role of those who teach to offer reality in a finished way, nor to become the subject of an alien exploration, but to accompany the path of self-knowledge of each of their students (Morris, 2021; Valério et al., 2021).

In the same way, the framework of an educational approach by competencies requires a vision of the objectives, contents, and evaluation criteria, in harmony. The objectives must be interpreted and developed in terms of competence (Makhmudov, 2020); these are the true purposes of the educational process. Likewise, the contents must be organized and prioritized to contribute to the development and acquisition of skills (Muratov, 2021). Here the teaching staff has a key role; I no longer must wonder what I am going to give in the first place. And regarding the evaluation criteria, these must play the role of interrelation link between the competencies that are defined, the objectives that are pursued, and the contents that have been planned (Brundiens et al., 2021).

The decision on competency-based teaching also raises changes in what refers to the management and organization of educational centers (Huynh et al., 2019). The following questions are very pertinent:

- Can the educational system take on these new challenges with its current organizational and operational structures? Are the modalities in which educational systems have been organized throughout a century adequate to respond adequately to the changes in present-day society? What needs to change? (MARY O’KEEFE, 2007, p.229)

In almost all countries it has been very difficult to become aware that the skills needed to run a school are not the same as those required, for example, to be a teacher. This, which could have been valid at other times, is today insufficient. Increasingly, it is essential to reconceive the essential aspects of the management of educational centers (Suarez-Fernandez de Miranda et al., 2020), which are not indifferent but facilitators or conditioning factors of the fulfillment of the objectives of education. This awareness still has a long way to go and deepen (Hilbrandt & Grubbauer, 2020).

Educational management has traditionally been a secondary aspect in the school, focused on its administrative processes and not professionalized (Shaturaev & Bekimbetova, 2021). This problem is due in part to the fact that management has been strictly linked to business and separated from education. But although the classroom is the privileged space of education, it is in the institution as a unit of meaning where educational quality is at stake (Aliyyah et al., 2020).

Today we speak of institutional autonomy, but when the centers are faced with decision-making, they collide with current organization models and management styles (Li et al., 2021). A review is necessary, but what would schools have to be like to carry it out?

Armenia et al. (2019), is one of the authors who has emphasized this problem and points out two interesting characteristics, which we summarize below:

Table 3: The features of the new school management and organization model

An organization that learns	One way of thinking about the organization and management of centers is from the paradigm of institutional learning and not from control, which means on the one hand recognizing and correcting the error (as a deviation from the objectives), but also make the organization more flexible by facilitating learning new procedures and new responses to new challenges. A flexible and hetero directed organization that not only accepts the challenge of environment but can take advantage of it as a motor of institutional transformation.
A management that leads	When it comes to dealing with change, schools have resistance issues and lack of flexibility. Education itself and culture have a relatively slow rate of change. Given this, the field of management is the one that has to do with the probability that once decisions are made, they are carried out effectively, a management that shows results and that drive towards the set goals. The specific profile of the task of efficient management is summarized in its ability to generate and sustain lines of action.

This same author poses two challenges for the management and organization of the centers:

- Confront massiveness, which translates into the need to professionalize management because the nature of the problems changed, the original models became inefficient, and the response of a homogeneous service entered crisis (Raithel et al., 2018).
- Respond to its results, which confronts us with the question: with what organization and management style are effective results achieved? (Zhou et al., 2019)

It should be noted that, although we are two decades away from these reflections, the concerns and intentions continue to be the same (in general terms); which tells us that these changes must be translated and put into action.

THE ROLE OF EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT FROM AND FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMPETENCES

“It tends to a pedagogical direction, aimed at increasing the learning and results of the school” (Papakostas et al., 2021; MARY O’KEEFE 2007, p 279)

Strategic educational management

To understand the multiple meanings of the term management, the following expressions have been proposed: piloting, innovation, exploration, continuous improvement, professionalization, identification of strengths and difficulties, thinking for action, pedagogical leadership, vision, communication, learning, building networks, anticipation, decision, evaluation (Jedaman et al., 2019). They all have something to do with participation, as recognition that management is an activity of collective actors (Menacho-Vargas et al., 2021).

The transformation in which we are immersed forces us to move towards strategic educational management as an alternative to traditional management (Chavarría-Bolaños et al., 2020). Here is a table with its main characteristics:

Table 4: Signs of the identity of strategic educational management

Strategic educational management	1. Centrality of the pedagogical.
	2. Skills to deal with the complex.
	3. Teamwork.
	4. Openness to learning and innovation.
	5. Professional advice and guidance.
	6. Organizational cultures united by a vision of the future.
	7. Reconfiguration, new skills, and professionalization.
	8. Systemic and strategic thinking and interventions.
	9. Organizational learning.
	10. pedagogical leadership.

Some reflections can be extracted from the previous table. In the first place, reconfiguration can only be tackled if it is promoted from the ability to work in teams, which make it possible

to share experiences, favoring spaces for exchange and innovation. In this way, that intelligent organization open to learning is built, which recognizes the need for these spaces to grow in participation and collective responsibility (Yaakob et al., 2019).

Second, educational management can be understood as a set of actions and theoretical-practical processes; it is a knowledge of synthesis capable of linking knowledge and action, tending to the continuous improvement of educational practices. It is a new way of understanding and leading the school organization (Raikov, 2019), which must recognize as one of its foundations the situational strategic calculation, in such a way that it becomes a process that generates specific decisions. Strategic management is the process by which we integrate strategic thinking and acting into creative practice (Sabaruddin et al., 2022).

Thirdly, educational management has to do with the resolution of conflicts, which arise between what is expected and what is contingent, and with the abandonment of simple visions to assume the complexity and uncertainty of the educational reality. Because educational management involves and encourages the integration of diverse knowledge, practices, and skills (Terziev et al., 2021).

The McClure, Poulin, Sovie, and Wandelt study (1983) maintains that "all educational management activities can be integrated into these three keys: reflection, decision, and leadership." It also identifies three inseparable and fundamental components of strategic educational management: "systemic and strategic thinking, pedagogical leadership, and organizational learning" (Huynh, 2022; Citaristi, 2022; Yoost, B. L., & Crawford 2021, pp. 27-29).

Management has evolved from management by events (assuring, reactive, non-anticipatory, individualistic) to participative management, based on management by objectives and results, and with the influence of leadership. This direction supposes an improvement of the management processes, presuming active participation of all, supported by the leadership of self-directed teams, where leadership is strengthened (Srivastava et al., 2020). The so-called management by values begins to be designed, which fills with meaning, humanizes, and completes, through shared values, the rest of the types of management that preceded it, without ignoring them (Elfert, 2019; Haydar, 2019; Patricia Benner, 1996, p. 332).

We effectively believe that this is the type of educational management that a competency-based learning model demands. At the same time, such a model can illuminate and guide current management practices (Bolton et al., 2020). So that a kind of interrelation between competencies and management is constituted. If we want to educate in competencies, the entire institution must be committed and inspired by this approach (Pham et al., 2020).

Competencies for strategic educational management

The competency approach seems to offer an innovative response related to the challenges of building new professionalism in education. Leading an organization requires new capacities from its managers, and new competencies that include the capacity for reflection, creativity, decision, leadership, and action (Jackson, 2019).

The dynamic and complex reality must be reconstructed in descriptive and explanatory models through processes of analysis and synthesis. The manager must identify the different patterns that manifest themselves under the various phenomena and specific cases. The specific conceptual models will then allow the development of interventions aimed at manipulating those variables that are within the manager's strategic action space (Bals et al., 2019).

In the same way, the intellectual capacity to understand phenomena as constitutive interdependencies of a system and, furthermore, articulated in chains of reciprocal causality is essential. From here it is possible for the manager to imagine and build alternative courses and scenarios of action intervention (Biberhofer et al., 2019).

The capacity for experimentation is relevant when it comes to placing managers in the very terms of the intervention, both from a professional and interpersonal point of view (Shum et al., 2018).

Finally, one of the main skills for those responsible for educational management is the ability to work as a team. Furthermore, it is essential that the manager be able to educate others in the development of this capacity. This supposes a reduction of isolation, which has traditionally characterized work in education, and an opening to complementarity, to the acceptance of others (Emerson & Berge, 2018).

For their part, Brundiers et al. (2021), in their study on pedagogical leadership, point out that the most valued competencies in managers are human and technical management, and underline the importance of training the manager as a pedagogical leader.

Management competence means clarity and consistency in decision-making. It implies that the leader must commit to improving teaching and educational practices, as a condition for achieving student learning (Jackson, 2019).

Competence of human nature has a priority place in education today. Managers demand a combination of emotional intelligence, empathy, communication, sensitivity, honesty, and openness. Leadership has, for these authors, an eminently humanistic nature insofar as it requires a commitment to educational values (Zheng et al., 2020).

Technical competence affects the mastery of the design and development of the program in educational institutions, involving experts who know the most representative elements to be applied, especially the meaning and impact that the improvement project is expected for the education of students (Falloon, 2020). This competence requires mastery of ICT media, virtual spaces, and other resources to contribute to the design and execution of creative and innovative improvement programs (pp. 94 and 95).

The competence that appears as transversal is that of leadership; because teamwork does not guarantee the gestation of new proposals if there is no capacity to land ideas in feasible projects. If there is no clear leadership capacity, it is difficult for autonomy and teamwork to bear fruit (Dzwigol et al., 2020).

Pedagogical and distributed leadership

A relevant OECD report (Improving school leadership) points out that “in many countries, there is a growing concern that the role of principals, designed for the needs of different age, may not be adequate to meet the challenges of leadership. That schools face in the 21st century” (Heikka et al., 2021; Patricia Benner et al., 20009; Patricia Benner, 1996, vol. 1, p. 272).

Dominguez et al. (2018), indicate that:

- The most representative leadership models to promote innovative processes in the Centers are transformational, emotional harmony, collaboration, distributed, etc., which consider leadership as a synthesis of multiple socio-relational realities, which place at the core of their identity the emotions and the needs of the people who make up the organization, acting as a generator of the integral development of the rest of the people in the Institution. (Patricia Benner et al. 1996: p.192)

Educational leadership or pedagogical management of schools is becoming, in the international context, a factor of the first order in the improvement of education (Kwan, 2020). Various international studies indicate this.

The Rostini et al. (2022), Report points out that good school leadership is a determining factor in the quality of education, for which excellent managers must be selected and trained (Campinha-Bacote, 1999, p. 319).

According to Schwarz et al. (2018), "the ability to improve a school establishment depends, in a relevant way, on management teams with leadership that actively contribute to energizing, supporting and encouraging its development, so that it can build its internal capacity of improvement" (p. 336).

In a general sense, we understand school leadership as “the task of mobilizing and influencing others to articulate and achieve the shared intentions and goals of the school” (Brion-Meisels & Alter, 2019; Sashkin and Sashkin, 2003. p. 3).

According to the IIEP text, leadership is a diverse set of pedagogical and innovative practices, which seek to facilitate, guide, and regulate complex processes of delegation, cooperation and training of teachers, managers and other people who work in education. Leadership practices activate educational organizations to recover the sense and the pedagogical mission, developed from objectives aimed at achieving significant learning for students (Jedaman et al. 2019; McClelland and Burnham, 1976.2, p 9).

The most relevant thing about leadership is that its potential is directly linked to deep learning; pedagogical leadership, "leadership centered on learning" (Blase & Blasé, 1999: Myran & Sutherland, 2019).

Management requires leadership practices to arrange, reflect, plan, direct, accompany, communicate, motivate, and educate in educational transformation. Building effective schools require pedagogical leaders who promote learning processes and help raise awareness and call for collaborative work (McNeill et al., 2018). Ultimately, leadership promotes generative

work. It is the dimension of strategic educational management that assumes that the changes to be undertaken require identifying and posing collective problems and evaluating them based on the values to be deepened, to achieve useful results (Lochmiller & Mancinelli, 2019).

We include the following table with some actions that favor leadership and, at the same time, enable and promote management for learning:

Table 5: Contribution of leadership practices and actions that favor it

Leadership practices are a means to:	Practices that favor the construction of leadership:
Generate organizational and social learning.	Inspire the need to generate transformations.
Collectively solve new problems.	Generate a vision of the future.
Redefine values.	Communicate that vision of the future.
Adjust action processes to achieve those values.	Promote teamwork.
Stimulate the development of other forms of understand and act.	Provide guidance that develops the spirit of achievement.
Expand continuous improvement processes. Develop and sustain learning circles deep.	Consolidate progress in transformations.
Solve extended and continuous processes of training to strengthen complex skills, both individual and collective.	Update learning and accumulate knowledge.

In the program promoted by the OECD, the improvement of school leadership goes through four main lines of action: (re) defining responsibilities; distribute school leadership; acquiring the skills and competencies necessary for effective leadership; and making leadership an attractive profession. These topics constitute the chapters of the cited volume (Shahbal et al., 2022; Brivio et al., 2021; Patricia Benner et al., 2009; Grossman, 2005, vol. 1, 22).

The action of the leader must also be placed in the improvement of teaching practices, to contribute to the improvement of student achievement (Epstein et al., 2019). This task, which has been understood in many countries as far from the management's sphere of competence, is fundamental because if teaching is a determining factor in student learning, directors must create conditions for teachers to better carry out their work (McNeill et al., 2018).

Another interesting aspect of the exercise of management as leadership is to understand it as a practice distributed throughout the organization; it is about sharing leadership, generating common responsibilities (Schwarz et al., 2018). This means advocating for leadership distributed among all the members of the institution because the improvement of educational quality cannot fall exclusively on the management (Alharbi et al., 2022; Heikka et al., 2021).

As Jackson, (2019) explain, "distributed leadership transfers the exercise of influence from the top of the organizational hierarchy to the work teams themselves and to the teachers". In this line, Sá & Serpa (2022) underline the impact of participatory leadership aimed at stimulating teacher initiative (Benner et al., 2009: p. 91).

If we want an organization that works, more people are needed than the director; it is required to develop leadership capacity in others, commitment, and collaborative work. This amounts to expanding the human capacity of the institution, not giving more comfort or less

responsibility to the formal leader. On the contrary, this represents more demand for him, as he must coordinate and supervise all that dispersed leadership (Heikka et al., 2021). This way of understanding and practicing leadership tends to and reinforces what has recently been called a "professional learning community" (Jensen, 2006: McGregor 1960, p. 34).

"When there is the distribution of leadership, the commitment of peers is more influential than when there is only administrative leadership" (Heikka et al., 2021). Certainly, leadership exerts a greater influence on learning and educational improvement when it is distributed. However, this is of little relevance if good forms of distribution are not established: what tasks are distributed, levels of distribution and according to what patterns.

Various studies have proliferated on pedagogical and distributed leadership in the last decade. As can be seen, there is clear feedback between the good management of centers and these practices of pedagogical and distributed leadership. At the same time, this affects the improvement of educational quality in general and the significant learning of students. In this work, we have consulted Torres et al. (2022), and Youngs (2022).

CONCLUSIONS

As we pointed out at the beginning, the motivation for carrying out this study was to investigate an educational reality that is increasingly complex and changing, where the demands are heterogeneous, and the trend is inclining towards the need for greater emphasis on meaningful and relevant learning for all students (Jenn et al., 2022).

One of the conclusions of this work is that it is necessary for the management of educational institutions to accompany these changes that occur at a social and educational level. New teaching-learning models appear here, where the competency-based model is located.

The purpose then, without wishing to exhaust the question, was to contribute to the debate about the improvement of educational quality through innovation and to analyze what is the role that the management of centers plays in this process that we believe consists of transforming schemes and old models in education and management. In this line, the competencies approach was shown to be transversal, because we could see what a contribution means as a teaching model as well as a management model.

This is the product of conceiving organizations as units of meaning, and not as isolated compartments of students, teachers, managers, and families. The feedback that we observe between management and learning through the competency model is due to this obligation to build learning communities around educational systems.

Trying to respond to the stated objectives, we can say that the current virtue of the competency-based learning model lies fundamentally in the fact that it helps students to be autonomous in their learning and assume that the construction of knowledge is in their hands. The student must think of himself as the protagonist of the foundation of values, knowledge, and attitudes toward reality. In the same way, this model is a benchmark in the conviction that the education of people must be comprehensive.

The competency approach also shows us that truth is not something static, but that we collectively participate in its own dynamism. Likewise, it places us in the face of the construction of our individual and collective identity. It is the primary purpose of education to place ourselves before this question that history asks us: who are we?

Regarding the management of centers, we have been able to elucidate what type of management the implementation of this teaching-learning modality demands. Strategic educational management leads, within the framework of an organization that learns; that includes thought and action, tending to the creative and humanizing practice of education.

We have also explored what skills those responsible for educational centers should have, grouped, and summarized into management, human and technical skills. We especially focus on leadership as a core competency, which is a global political priority; pedagogical leadership (open to learning) and distributed (among all members of the educational community) as the key to directing current organizations.

Finally, it should be noted that although this research is of a theoretical nature, in a second instance it could be translated into practical results, as other studies of the same type of show.

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